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GAMEHEARTS

Videogame for EDI

Project: Games, Heritage, Arts, & Sport: the economic, social, and cultural value of the European videogame ecosystem. GAMEHEARTS

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Author(s): Ana Klock, Shariful Islam, Juho Hamari (TAU)

Reviewer(s): Patrycja Klimas (WUEB), Katharine Sarikakis (UNIVIE)

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1. PROJECT SUMMARY

GAMEHEARTS seeks to maximise the value of the European video game industry ecosystems (hereafter, EVGIE) within a wider social context of the creative and cultural industries (hereafter, CCI). This considers the importance of the EVGIE in contributing to economic growth, job creation, physical and mental wellbeing, and social and cultural cohesion, by particularly focusing on how a stronger and closer working relationship between more the traditional and emergent cultural sectors, can work better to create more inclusive and socially responsible cultural experiences. The consortium offers policy recommendations and roadmaps setting out how the EVGIE can and should develop, and where it could act as a driver for sustained innovation and economic growth. It will utilise an evidence-based approach that focuses not just on video game development, but rather adopts a holistic ecosystem approach, utilising both established and more innovative methodologies, to consider the competitiveness and development of the EVGIE, and how video game know-how and technologies could drive innovation in the wider CCI. In doing so, GAMEHEARTS will develop ‘ludic experiences’, to explore possibilities of more inclusive, engaging, and empowering cultural experiences. Working across seven work packages the universities of Salford (UK), Tampere (Finland), Vienna (Austria), Breda University of Applied Sciences (Netherlands), and Wroclaw University of Economics and Business (Poland) will work in partnership with Ubisoft (France) and other major video game partners and associations (including the VGE & EGDF) to explore current and future trends in the EVGIE. Beyond this, we work with certain cultural case study partners to consider how game-related technologies and practices are, and could be used to, increase access to heritage, the arts, and sport.

2. INTRODUCTION

This report presents the design of the developed video game aimed at fostering inclusion for youth through collaborative gameplay. It builds directly on the iterative workshops and evaluations described in the previous deliverable (D5.3 Player-centred videogames prototypes¹), but here the focus lies on presenting the videogame narrative and design.

The central contribution is demonstrating how a structured, engaging, and playful experience can support social capital and cohesion among young people by embedding aspects of Positive Youth Development (PYD) developmental principles into interactive systems.

2.1 THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

The player-centred prototypes that preceded this report, as well as this game itself, are both based on the PYD framework, which approaches young people as individuals possessing skills, strengths, and potential that can be nurtured and cultivated within their social environments (Lerner, 2009). Interactions between the individual and their context, often facilitated through youth programs, give rise to five key developmental outcomes, commonly referred to as the 5Cs, which support youth in achieving personal growth, well-being, and meaningful contribution. These five outcomes are competence, confidence, connection, character, and caring (Roth & Brooks-Gunn, 2003; Lerner et al., 2005), presented in Figure 1 and detailed as:

- **Competence** refers to the youth's perception of their own abilities across social, academic, cognitive, and vocational domains;
- **Confidence** refers to a positive sense of self-worth, self-efficacy, and trust in one's ability to overcome challenges;
- **Connection** refers to the reciprocal, positive relationships with peers, family members, and community institutions;
- **Character** refers to developing a strong moral compass, ethical decision-making, and respect for societal values; and
- **Caring** refers to showing empathy, compassion, and concern for the well-being of others.

1 10.5281/zenodo.15649623

Figure 1. A developmental contextual view of PYD (Lerner et al., 2005).

2.2 PROTOTYPES REFINEMENT

Towards supporting social capital and cohesion, the idea of the videogame evolved from the original prototypes in which players needed to help Xeno, an alien who returned from a failed mission to find new resources to save their planet, towards helping Xeno to understand what has happened and what to do next.

However, after collecting feedback during a three-hour workshop with 13 participants aged 18 to 26 within Tampere University premises, we noticed that many participants expressed a desire to play as the alien protagonist, Xeno, demonstrating strong engagement with the character and narrative and highlighting the potential for identification and empathy through

metaphorical storytelling. Such observations informed refinements to the prototypes and, consequentially, the videogame, including a shift from a single non-playable protagonist to allowing all players to choose from different types of aliens with unique skills. Moreover, the videogame is designed for five players, as suggested by our partners during the prototype phase (i.e., youth work centre, game designers and researchers in game studies (Sundvik et al., 2024)), to ensure meaningful participation while maintaining group cohesion.

3. VIDEOGAME FOR EQUITY, DIVERSITY, AND INCLUSION (EDI)

This chapter presents the design, narrative, and technical implementation of *Uncommon Ground*, a hybrid collaborative videogame. The game serves as both a digital and social experience, combining real-world collaboration with online interaction to support the development of social, cognitive, and emotional skills in youth. Through carefully designed mechanics, storytelling, and user interface, *Uncommon Ground* encourages participants to communicate, negotiate, and make collective decisions, all while engaging with an interactive narrative that mirrors the challenges of cooperation, resilience, and shared problem-solving.

The following sections outline the main components that shape the gameplay experience. Section 3.1 describes the playing settings, explaining how the hybrid format integrates in-person facilitation with digital gameplay. Section 3.2 details the narrative framework that grounds the experience, introducing the storyline, characters, and progression structure that guide player engagement. Section 3.3 focuses on the playthrough sequence, illustrating how the mechanics of tasks, voting, and resource management embody the 5C elements of the Positive Youth Development (PYD) framework (i.e., Competence, Confidence, Connection, Character, and Caring). Finally, Section 3.4 provides the technical requirements and access details, describing the responsive web-based implementation, hosting environment, and public release plan. Together, these elements demonstrate how *Uncommon Ground* integrates narrative design, cooperative mechanics, and accessible technology to create a meaningful, research-informed gameplay experience.

3.1 PLAYING SETTINGS

The videogame is supposed to be a hybrid experience that combines real-life conversations and collaboration, with virtual videogame interaction and feedback. Players work together in the same room to progress in the narrative, allowing them to engage in discussion and see their actions reflected in the digital environment. These interactions are directly tied to the targeted skills and integrated into the storyline, while a facilitator supervises the activities to ensure smooth gameplay and maintain a safe environment for all participants.

3.2 NARRATIVE

The narrative is read by a facilitator at the beginning of the hybrid gaming session (or, in the future, by the players themselves, available after login when videogame is fully online):

The initial context

One sunny afternoon, a massive solar storm decided to throw a surprise party. Five unlucky aliens cruising near Earth were the guests of honour: fried systems, scrambled satellites, and their ships yanked out of orbit like a cosmic tug-of-war. Now, these unlikely strangers find themselves crash-landing somehow in the very same remote patch of Earth.

Their ships? Total scrap. Their tools? Wrecked. Their comms? Down for the count. Now they're stuck on an unfamiliar planet, surrounded by strange landscapes. There's only one way forward: Survive. Rebuild. Escape.

The alien crew

Thankfully, each of these aliens has a unique talent that help saving the day:

- **Glob, the Forageborg**, who can locate edible matter in any biome... though it is not always technically food.
- **Splintertron 9000**, who can identify, fell, and stack a tree before you finish saying "timber", but always leaves a tiny sapling behind.
- **Alloysius Crank**, who can sense metal vibrations and won't stop rambling about "the good old forge days".
- **Toolius Wrenchworthy**, who once invented three new tools in a day, named two of them, and won't explain what the third one does.
- **Dr. Fixle, the Ductapean**, who can fix anything with strips, glue, and the ancient art of slapping things until it works.

Alone, none of them stands a chance. But together, they just might make it.

The cards

The crew's got a lot on their plates if they want to survive, rebuild, and eventually escape: food runs to keep their energy up, collecting wood and metal to craft tools that make work easier, and digging through wreckage for anything that still sparks and might help patch the ships back together. And progress happens one random card at a time, describing the current top-priority task and its rewards.

The specialist role and energy recovery

While doing tasks drains energy from our heroes and gladly everyone luckily had their favourite protein bar before the crash, each alien brings their own special skill to the table that might optimize that energy use. For example, as Glob has a unique talent for finding snacks, food-related tasks tire them out less, and they don't need to eat as much to recover full energy. Same goes for Splintertron when it comes to wood, Alloysius for metal, Toolius for tools, and Dr. Fixle for ship-fixing. Still, no matter how skilled, they'll need to eat again eventually: no energy, no task. And since everything they collect goes into one big shared stash, they also have to agree who gets to eat and recharge.

Doing tasks

Once an alien volunteers for a task (and the rest give a thumbs-up, tentacle wiggle, or equivalent gesture of approval), they're locked in. No multitasking! That alien's busy for a whole turn, laser-focused on their mission until it's done. The good news is that every completed task earns unity points for the crew.

Shopping and skipping tasks

On top of that, while some tasks pop up again and again (like cosmic weeds), others are one-time-only opportunities. Of course, you don't need to do them all, but agree to skip those at your own risk (and pocket, as they cost unity points). More than that, unity points can also be traded by the crew for extra resources (because sometimes you really do need just one more chunk of food, wood, or metal) at a curious little shop run by a suspiciously friendly Area 51 enthusiast who doesn't ask too many questions.

The phases

As they progress, the journey unfolds from surviving to rebuilding, and from rebuilding to escaping. Each one of these three phases has different tasks that get progressively harder and conditions for moving forward. Piece by piece, task by task, snack by snack... the crew gets closer to flying back into space.

Therefore, the videogame is named *Uncommon Ground*, drawing from the idea of finding connection in unexpected or diverse social spaces, while also alluding to the role-playing setting in which all players are a different type of alien who are collectively indeed not in a familiar and common ground. The narrative aims to encourage strategic and collaborative **competence** by challenging players to plan, prioritise, and execute tasks essential for the aliens' survival, from foraging for food and gathering resources to repairing their ships. It fosters **confidence** as players see the impact of their decisions, successfully complete tasks, and contribute to the crew's shared progress, experiencing mastery in both individual and group roles. Through cooperative missions and the need to coordinate energy, resources, and skills, the game promotes **connection**, helping players build communication, negotiation, and teamwork as they navigate the alien crew's interdependence. **Character** is developed as players face ethical choices about how to allocate limited resources, assign tasks, and balance individual needs with the collective good. These moments invite moral reasoning and foster a sense of fairness, integrity, and responsibility toward others. **Caring**, in turn, is cultivated as players empathise with the aliens' unique strengths and limitations, offering support and encouragement to ensure that the entire crew survives, rebuilds, and ultimately escapes. By integrating these elements into its narrative and mechanics, *Uncommon Ground* provides an engaging platform for youth to develop social, strategic, and collaborative skills while experiencing a rich story of teamwork and resilience.

3.3 PLAYTHROUGH

Following the facilitator's introduction of the narrative, players are invited to access the responsive web-based videogame either through a computer provided on-site or using their own personal devices. Upon arrival, the landing page (as Figure 2a) shows the GAMEHEARTS logo and the "*Uncommon Ground*" videogame name at the top bar, and prompts each participant to log in with an individual account. For new players, the "Register" option allows them to create credentials by selecting a username and password, as Figure 2b. The username functions as an in-game identifier, visible to all participants during the session to indicate who is playing which character, while the password enables players to return for subsequent sessions with the same account if desired.

(a) **Figure 2.** Landing (a) and Registration (b) pages

(b)

On both pages, a bottom navigation bar provides access to the “Credits” section. This link redirects players to a dedicated page that acknowledges the support of the European Union’s Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme, credits the image creators from the FlatIcon website (<https://www.flaticon.com/>) and the Tampere University research team, and specifies the usage licence of the game (CC BY-NC-SA), as illustrated in Figure 3.

Uncommon Ground

▼ Project Information

This game was developed thanks to the support of the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme under grant agreement No 101132543. The game and its content were developed by researchers at Tampere University only and do not necessarily reflect any collective opinion of the GAMEHEARTS consortium, nor do they reflect the official opinion of the European Commission. Neither the European Commission nor any person acting on behalf of the European Commission is responsible for the use which might be made of the following information.

Tampere University research team:

Juho Hamari
Ana Klock
Shariful Islam
Faith Ilesanmi
Nevena Sicevic
Ylva Sundvik

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BY: credit must be given to the creator.

NC: Only noncommercial uses of the work are permitted.

SA: Adaptations must be shared under the same terms.

Home

Figure 3. Credits page

After logging in with their credentials, players are directed to the group selection page (see Figure 4). Here, participants enter a code provided by the facilitator, which assigns them to a group of five players in the current gaming session. In future iterations of the fully online version, this functionality will enable players to generate and share codes themselves, allowing them to form groups with peers and ensure they join the same gaming session.

Uncommon Ground Logout

Group

Group Code:

Enter Group

Figure 4. Group selection page

Once the group code has been entered, players proceed to the character selection screen. This step builds on the earlier narrative introduction by providing a more detailed presentation of each alien. In addition to outlining their unique abilities (such as gathering food, harvesting wood, detecting metal, crafting tools, or repairing ships) the page also reveals personal motivations for urgent returning to their home planets. These backstories serve to enhance representation and foster empathy, giving players both a functional and emotional connection to their chosen character, as detailed below and illustrated in Figure 5:

- **Glob, the Forageborg**

A native Flavourxian, Glob has 16 nostrils that allow them to sniff out snacks from light-years away, and a super eye that can spot a crumb in any asteroid field. Right now, their pet Zlurp is waiting for them to come home, loyally guarding the treat cabinet like a furry little sentinel.

- **Splintertron 9000**

Born on the forest-covered planet Arboricon-6, Splintertron 9000 comes from a long line of log-harvesters with hyper-sensitive bark detection. Despite their profession, they have a deep love for nature, and they're really worried their bonsai tree at home will need watering in the next two days.

- **Alloysius Crank**

From the mineral-rich world of Scroppia, Alloysius can detect rock vibrations even underground, and tell you exactly what kind of ore is crying. They were on their way to their best friend's birthday party (featuring karaoke and magnesium cake) before the crash. The gift might be lost, but they still hope to make it in time.

- **Toolius Wrenchworthy**

Straight from the industrious moon of Tinkerthon, Toolius belongs to a species wired for invention. Their brain has blueprints baked in from birth, and their many hands work with lightspeed efficiency. They promised their brother they'd help build a new gravity-defying cottage tonight, and they never miss a blueprint bonding session.

- **Dr. Fixle, the Ductapean**

Equipped with neuro-flexible antennae that interface with malfunctioning tech, Dr. Fixle can spot a fault before the ship even knows it's sick. A proud graduate of the Galactic Institute of Oopsology, they were supposed to be celebrating tonight with their coworkers a shiny new repair patent, with their name stamped all over it.

←Back
 Uncommon Ground
Logout

Select Your Alien

Select which character you would like to play as below. Multiple players can choose the same alien, but the game can only start once each alien is represented by one player.

<p>Glob, the forageborg</p> <p>Special ability: Finding food</p> <p>A native Flavouxian, Glob has 16 nostrils that allow them to sniff out snacks from light-years away, and a super eye that can spot a crumb in any asteroid field. Right now, their pet Zurp is waiting for them to come home, loyally guarding the treat cabinet like a furry little sentinel.</p> <p style="text-align: right; font-size: small;">Selected by: john <input type="button" value="Select"/></p>	<p>Splintertron, 9000</p> <p>Special ability: Finding wood</p> <p>Born on the forest-covered planet Arboricon-6, Splintertron 9000 comes from a long line of log-harvesters with hyper-sensitive bark detection. Despite their profession, they have a deep love for nature, and they're really worried their bonsai tree at home will need watering in the next two days.</p> <p style="text-align: right; font-size: small;">Selected by: xi <input type="button" value="Select"/></p>	<p>Alloysius, Gank</p> <p>Special ability: Finding minerals</p> <p>From the mineral-rich world of Scrapplia, Alloysius can detect rock vibrations even underground, and tell you exactly what kind of ore is crying. They were on their way to their best friend's birthday party (featuring karaoke and magnesium cake) before the crash. The gift might be lost, but they still hope to make it in time.</p> <p style="text-align: right; font-size: small;">Selected by: dev <input type="button" value="Select"/></p>	<p>Toolius, Wrenchworthy</p> <p>Special ability: Building tools</p> <p>Straight from the industrious moon of Tinkerthon, Toolius belongs to a species wired for invention. Their brain has blueprints baked in from birth, and their many hands work with lightspeed efficiency. They promised their brother they'd help build a new gravity-defying cottage tonight, and they never miss a blueprint bonding session.</p> <p style="text-align: right; font-size: small;">Selected by: asia <input type="button" value="Unselect"/></p>	<p>Dr. Fixle, the Ductapean</p> <p>Special ability: Repairing ships</p> <p>Equipped with neuro-flexible antennae that interface with malfunctioning tech, Dr. Fixle can spot a fault before the ship even knows it's sick. A proud graduate of the Galactic Institute of Oopsoology, they were supposed to be celebrating tonight with their coworkers a shiny new repair patent, with their name stamped all over it.</p> <p style="text-align: right; font-size: small;">Selected by: mpotu <input type="button" value="Select"/></p>
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Figure 5. Alien selection page

On this page, the top bar provides two essential options: a “Back” button in the upper-left corner, which returns players to the group selection page should they mistype the group code, and a “Logout” option, which allows participants to withdraw from the session at any time, consistent with the principles of the informed consent agreed upon before gameplay. The interface updates dynamically as character selections are made, providing real-time feedback to all members of the group. Each participant may select only one character, and the “Start” button at the bottom of the screen becomes active only when all five players have chosen distinct roles. If two or more players select the same alien, the system highlights the overlap by displaying usernames, prompting participants to negotiate and resolve the conflict. In hybrid settings, this discussion takes place face-to-face, while in future fully online sessions it may be supported by external communication tools such as chat, audio, or video platforms. Once all conflicts are resolved and every player has selected a character, the group may press the “Start” button, which redirects all participants to the videogame’s main page, as Figure 6.

At this main page, the “Back” option in the upper-left corner is disabled, as renegotiating alien characters is no longer possible once the game has begun. The remainder of the top bar remains unchanged, displaying the GAMEHEARTS logo, the name of the videogame, and the “Logout” option. Directly below, the interface shows the current phase and its title (Phase 1:

Survive; Phase 2: Rebuild; Phase 3: Escape), following the overarching narrative. In the centre of this page, players see a deck of cards marked with the GAMEHEARTS logo and a “Ready” button below it, which each of them must click when prepared to draw a task card. The task card will only be drawn if all players are ready. While players are not ready (i.e., they have not individually clicked the “Ready” button, or they clicked the “Unready” button which becomes available instead of the “Ready” button once they click the latest), two additional options are available: “Store” and “Health Recovery.”

To the left of the card deck, icons represent the tools that must be crafted during the current phase (i.e., primitive spear, axe, pickaxe, and hammer), initially displayed as silhouettes to indicate that they are not yet built. These tools will later support the collection of food, wood, and metal, as well as ship repairs in subsequent phases. To the right of the deck, the interface displays the team’s collective resources: food, wood, metal, debris, and unity points. These counters begin at zero, alongside indicators of the required thresholds for advancing to the next phase (15 food, 15 wood, 15 metal, 5 debris – being one for each spaceship of the aliens, and 25 unity points). These values were defined during playtesting to ensure a minimum onboarding period of approximately ten minutes in Phase 1. Finally, at the bottom of the interface, players can view the usernames and avatars of all participants, along with health indicators. Each player begins the game at full health (10/10), consistent with the narrative in which they had eaten a snack prior to crash-landing. To help individuals identify their own status, the interface underlines the username of the player currently logged in. For example, in Figure 6 the underlined username “asia” indicates the active player viewing that screen. On this page, the top bar provides two essential options: a “Back” button in the upper-left corner, which returns players to the group selection page should they mistype the group code, and a “Logout” option, which allows participants to withdraw from the session at any time, consistent with the principles of the informed consent agreed upon before gameplay. The interface updates dynamically as character selections are made, providing real-time feedback to all members of the group. Each participant may select only one character, and the “Start” button at the bottom of the screen becomes active only when all five players have chosen distinct roles. If two or more players select the same alien, the system highlights the overlap by displaying usernames, prompting participants to negotiate and resolve the conflict. In hybrid settings, this discussion takes place face-to-face, while in future fully online sessions it may be supported by external communication tools such as chat, audio, or video platforms. Once all conflicts are resolved and every player has selected a character, the group may press the “Start” button, which redirects all participants to the videogame’s main page, as Figure 6.

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Figure 6. Videogame’s main page

Once all players have clicked and remained “Ready,” the videogame automatically draws a random task card, as shown in Figure 7. Each task card contains a title (e.g., *Collect berries*), an image, a description outlining its rewards (such as gaining three units of food and three unity points) and its consequences (e.g., the specialist alien loses one health point as they use less energy to do that task, while a non-specialist loses two; additionally, the assigned alien becomes unavailable to perform subsequent tasks for a designated number of turns, reflecting the time spent on the mission). The card also includes a penalty for skipping, applied if the group decides not to undertake the task. The list of all tasks for these cards is included in Appendix A. At the bottom of the card, two options are displayed: players who are available and willing to take on the task may select the “Volunteer” button, while those who prefer to avoid the task may propose a “Suggest Skip” action, provided players have sufficient unity points to cover the penalty. Each player may only volunteer themselves; the decision on who ultimately undertakes the task must therefore be negotiated collectively within the group. Likewise, a player already engaged in another task cannot volunteer again until they are free.

These mechanics map directly to the PYD framework. When specialists complete tasks within their area of expertise, they demonstrate **competence**, using their unique strengths more efficiently. Volunteering builds **confidence**, as players take initiative and see the impact of their choices. Negotiating who should act or whether to skip fosters **connection**, highlighting the importance of group dialogue and cooperation. Balancing the costs of action with long-term goals cultivates **character**, as players must consider responsibility and fairness. Finally, the skip option underscores **caring**, since players often justify it as a way to protect the health and energy of the group. In this way, each task card becomes a practical opportunity for youth to practice all five C’s through collaborative play.

Figure 7. Task card page

Whenever a player volunteers to undertake a task or proposes skipping it, a voting sequence is triggered. If multiple players volunteer or suggest skipping at the same time, the voting order is always based on who clicked one of these actions first. All participants receive a pop-up notification indicating which player has suggested which action, be it volunteering for or skipping the task (see Figure 8a). Each player must then register their response by agreeing or disagreeing. Once an individual has cast their vote, they wait for the remaining group members to do the same, as illustrated in Figure 8b. The suggested action is implemented only if there is unanimous agreement among all players. If unanimity is not achieved, the group is returned to the task card page with the same challenge still active. The task must then be resolved either by confirming a volunteer to complete it or, if sufficient unity points are available, by unanimously agreeing to skip it.

Figure 8. Voting prompt (a) and Waiting for other players (b) pop-up windows

This voting mechanic embodies the PYD framework in several ways. It strengthens **connection** by requiring open dialogue and consensus, while also fostering **character** as players must weigh fairness and group responsibility in their choices. The need for unanimous approval reflects **caring**, since players must respect each other's well-being and perspectives before proceeding. Successfully negotiating who should act or whether to skip reinforces **confidence**, as youth see the value of their contributions, and **competence**, as they learn to navigate structured group decision-making. Thus, the voting process not only advances gameplay, but also creates meaningful opportunities to apply all 5Cs.

Figure 9. Videogame's main page with a timed pop-up indicating that voting has passed

Once a task has been resolved, players are automatically redirected to the main page (see Figure 9, which illustrates the case where all players agreed with the volunteer proposed in Figure 8a). The interface is immediately updated to reflect the outcome: collective resources increase according to the rewards specified on the card, while the volunteer's health decreases

as indicated. To signal temporary unavailability, the avatar of the volunteering player is displayed in black and white for the number of turns corresponding to the recovery time. Moreover, the progress on the right sidebar (i.e., winning conditions) is displayed through both percentage-based progression bars and colour coding. Each bar visually represents the proportion of items collected relative to the winning condition for advancing to the next phase. The colour system provides quick feedback:

- **Red bar** - indicates that less than half of the required amount has been collected (e.g., fewer than 8 of 15 units for food, wood, or metal; fewer than 3 of 5 units for debris; or fewer than 13 of 25 unity points);
- **Yellow bar** – indicates progress above half but still below the full requirement (e.g., 14 of 15 for food, wood, or metal; 4 of 5 for debris; or 24 of 25 unity points); and
- **Green bar** – indicates that the requirement has been met or exceeded.

This system ensures that all players can easily monitor collective progress at a glance, reinforcing awareness of shared objectives and motivating cooperation. In the example shown in Figure 9, the group’s food and unity points have each increased by three and are now with a red progress bar, based on the task from Figure 7, while the volunteering player (john, per Figure 8a) has lost one health point and is marked as unavailable. If the group had instead chosen to skip the task, the corresponding penalty – three unity points – would have been deducted from the collective pool. To support transparency, the confirmation pop-up indicating that the vote passed remains visible for five seconds before the game allows players to proceed by drawing a new card (“Ready”) or selecting the “Store” or “Health Recovery” options.

Figure 10. Videogame’s main page showing how many players are ready

While a player has not yet selected “Ready,” they may access the “Store” and “Health Recovery” options. The store allows players to purchase resources (food, wood, and metal, see Figure 11) which serve dual purposes: they are required for meeting the phase’s victory conditions (as in the right sidebar), and they are also necessary for recovering health (i.e., food) and crafting tools (i.e., wood and metal). Each resource can be purchased at a cost of two unity points per unit.

Figure 11. Store page

When a player wishes to purchase resources and has sufficient unity points, they can increase the desired amount of a resource by clicking the “+” button, which raises the proposed purchase by one unit at a time. The maximum purchase allowed is half of the group’s available unity points. For example, in Figure 11 the group has a total of 14 unity points, allowing the purchase of up to 7 resource units. The “-” button decreases the suggested amount by one unit, down to a minimum of zero. Once the player defines the quantity, they can suggest the purchase to the group. This prompts all participants with a voting window (see Figure 12), even if they are already marked as “Ready” to continue play.

Figure 12. Store voting prompt

Similar to task voting, purchases suggested at the store are subject to a unanimous approval process: if one player does not agree with it, the purchase fails (Figure 13a). Therefore, all players must agree before the purchase is finalised (Figure 13b). This store mechanic aims to reinforce players' **competence** by negotiating purchases through practice budgeting and managing shared resources, and **character**, since proposals must balance fairness with group needs rather than individual preference. The unanimous voting rule reinforces **connection** and **caring**, ensuring that each decision accounts for the well-being of all players. Finally, when a suggestion is successfully approved, players build **confidence**, as they see that their initiative can shape group outcomes in meaningful ways.

Figure 13. Voting prompt results as either failed (a) or passed (b) pop-up windows

During playtesting, players also proposed potential expansions to this feature that were not implemented in the current version due to time constraints, but remain feasible for future development, especially given its Creative Commons licence. One suggestion was to allow players to sell surplus resources for unity points, with a lower return rate (e.g., one unity point per unit) to preserve game balance. Another idea was to introduce the option to purchase the removal of specific card types. For instance, in late-game scenarios where food and unity point thresholds are already met but wood and metal remain scarce, players could pay to prevent food cards from reappearing in the random draw.

Similar to the “Store” option, players may individually access the “Health Recovery” feature whenever they are not marked as “Ready” for the current turn. This page displays all players whose health is below maximum, and participants can propose restoring health for themselves or others. If sufficient food resources are available, the proposer can increase the amount of recovery by clicking the “+” button, which raises the number of hearts by one unit at a time. The maximum recovery allowed is half of the group’s available food supply. For example, in Figure 14 the group has a total of nine food units, enabling recovery of up to three health points. Each player’s health is capped at ten, ensuring that no participant can exceed the maximum. The “-” button decreases the proposed amount, down to a minimum of zero.

Figure 14. Health recovery page

Once the desired amount of recovery has been defined, the player submits the proposal to the group. As with the store, this triggers a unanimous voting sequence: all players receive a pop-up confirmation window (see Figure 15), even if they are already set as “Ready” to continue. The recovery is only implemented if every participant agrees.

Figure 15. Health recovery voting prompt

This mechanic reinforces the PYD framework in multiple ways. Proposing recovery for oneself or others highlights **caring**, demonstrating that group well-being is a shared responsibility. Managing the limited food supply develops **competence**, as players must make strategic trade-offs. The unanimous approval process fosters **connection**, requiring agreement and trust among participants. Choosing how much to recover cultivates **character**, as players weigh fairness and sustainability in resource allocation. Finally, successfully initiating and validating a recovery action builds **confidence**, as youth see their decisions directly protect and sustain the group.

In addition to collecting the resources required to meet the winning conditions displayed on the right sidebar, players must also craft the tools shown on the left sidebar in order to advance to the next phase. These tools (i.e., spear, axe, pickaxe, and hammer) are essential for tasks in subsequent stages and require specific amounts of wood and metal to produce. When a crafting card is drawn (see Figure 16), the group must determine whether they have the necessary resources to complete the action or whether they are obliged to skip it. To maintain balance, the videogame ensures that crafting cards never appear as the very first draws of the first phase. This game design gives players the chance to gather the resources needed either to craft (wood and metal) or to skip (unity points). If the group lacks the required materials (whether because the early random cards did not provide enough wood and metal, or because these resources were already spent on another tool), they must skip the task. For example, as illustrated in Figure 16, the hammer cannot be built because the group has only two units of wood (instead of three) and no metal (instead of two). In this situation, the “Volunteer” button is replaced by a disabled “No resources” option, while the skip action remains possible since the group has ten unity points available. However, if the group lacks the resources to either craft or skip, the game issues a “Game Over” message, signalling that progress is no longer possible.

This mechanic reinforces several aspects of the PYD framework. The need to prepare for future requirements builds **competence**, as players must plan resource collection strategically. The challenge of crafting despite limited resources fosters **confidence**, teaching players to adapt to constraints. Negotiating whether to craft or skip highlights **connection**, since the decision must be unanimous and impacts everyone’s progress. Choosing when to conserve or spend materials cultivates **character**, encouraging responsibility and long-term thinking. Finally, the possibility of sacrificing immediate progress to protect the group’s survival reflects **caring**, ensuring that decisions account for collective wellbeing.

 Uncommon Ground
Logout

PHASE 1: SURVIVE

Primitive Spear

Primitive Axe

Primitive Pickaxe

Primitive Hammer

MAKE HAMMER

BENEFITS:
+

CONSEQUENCES:
-
- OR
-
Chosen alien is out for 1 turn

SKIPPING PENALTY:
-

NO RESOURCES
SUGGEST SKIP

Food
 6/15

Wood
 2/15

Metal
 0/15

Debris
 1/5

Points
 10/25

john

 8/10

xi

 9/10

dev

 10/10

asia

 10/10

mpofu

 9/10

Figure 16. Crafting task with insufficient resources, requiring a skip

Once all winning conditions of Phase 1 are fulfilled – namely, the collective collection of 15 units of food, 15 units of wood, 15 units of metal, 5 units of debris, and 25 unity points (as shown on the right sidebar), together with the successful crafting of all four primitive tools – the game provides feedback indicating that the group has advanced from the *Survive* phase (Phase 1) to the *Rebuild* phase (Phase 2), as seen in Figure 17.

Figure 17. Phase transition prompt

This confirmation prompt is displayed to all players, requiring each participant to acknowledge the transition before the game continues. This step ensures that the progression accommodates different reading speeds and guarantees that every player is aware of the successful completion of the first phase.

Upon advancing to Phase 2, the card deck expands to include more advanced tasks that go beyond basic resource collection without tools (e.g., berries, twigs, rocks). New tasks involve activities such as hunting animals for food, chopping trees for wood, and mining boulders for metal. As illustrated in Figure 18, some of these cards now specify the tool required to complete the task. The tool may be either in its primitive form (crafted in Phase 1) or its advanced version (upgraded from primitive form as a crafting card or still unavailable in Phase 2). Following the established logic, when a player volunteers for such a task, they take the necessary tool with them. Both the player and the tool then become unavailable for one or more turns (as defined by the card), depending on the task duration. To maintain balance and avoid locking progression, the videogame prevents two consecutive cards of the same type that would require the same tool. For example, if the first card of Phase 2 is *Hunting rabbit* (Figure 18) and the group chooses not to skip it, the subsequent card will not be another hunting activity, since that would again require the same tool, which would be unavailable doing the first card. Instead, it may be a different food-related task, such as *Collecting berries*, which does not depend on tools. This preserves meaningful decision-making: although the group still faces the limitation that the specialist alien (e.g., Glob) cannot volunteer twice in a row, they are not blocked from continuing to make progress.

Uncommon Ground
Logout

PHASE 2: REBUILD

Primitive
Spear

Primitive
Axe

Primitive
Pickaxe

Primitive
Hammer

HUNT RABBIT

BENEFITS:
+ 🍖 🍖 🍖 AND + 🥚 🥚 🥚

CONSEQUENCES:
- ❤️ for 🧟 OR
- ❤️ ❤️ for 🧟 🧟 🧟
Chosen alien is out for 1 turn

SKIPPING PENALTY:
- 🥚 🥚

REQUIRED TOOL:
🔪 OR 🛠️

VOLUNTEER
SUGGEST SKIP

Food
 25/20

Wood
 19/20

Metal
 13/20

Debris
 4/0

Points
 34/35

john
❤️ 5/10

xi
❤️ 1/10

dev
❤️ 4/10

asia
❤️ 4/10

mpofu
❤️ 4/10

Figure 18. Task card page, during Phase 2

As seen in Figure 18, the overall game design and mechanics remain consistent with Phase 1, with only a few adjustments introduced in Phase 2. First, the crafted tools displayed on the left sidebar must now be upgraded to advanced versions through dedicated crafting task cards. Second, some task cards themselves specify the use of a tool, which becomes temporarily unavailable while the assigned player completes the task, as seen in Figure 19.

Figure 19. Videogame's main page during Phase 2, showcasing when tool is unavailable

Finally, the resource thresholds displayed on the right sidebar are updated to reflect the requirements for advancing to Phase 3. To progress, players must collectively gather 20 units of food, 20 units of wood, and 20 units of metal. These targets represent an additional five units for each resource beyond the Phase 1 requirement, while still accounting for the fact that resources are also consumed when recovering health and upgrading tools. The

unity point threshold increases to 35, ten points more than in the previous phase. Debris functions differently in Phase 2. Rather than serving only as a static requirement, they become consumables needed for each *Repairing Hull* task, since they are required to mend the bodies of the five individual spaceships before moving to Phase 3. Thus, the five debris collected in Phase 1 are now expended during repairs, and the new winning condition is to reduce this number from five to zero. In addition, players continue to have access to the “Store” and “Health Recovery” options before marking themselves as ready for the game turn. Both features operate in the same way as in Phase 1, maintaining continuity in the mechanics while supporting strategic resource and health management. Similarly, a confirmation prompt (functioning like that in Figure 17) appears once all Phase 2 objectives are met, ensuring all players acknowledge its completion before Phase 3 begins.

Within Phase 2, the features collectively embody the PYD framework. Upgrading tools and managing materials foster **competence**, as players learn to balance short-term needs with long-term goals. Taking responsibility for repairing ships and allocating scarce resources highlights **character**, encouraging fairness and foresight. Negotiating actions through unanimous voting reinforces **connection**, emphasising trust and cooperation. The possibility of restoring teammates’ health illustrates **caring**, as group wellbeing is prioritised. Finally, achieving increasingly complex objectives strengthens **confidence**, showing players that they can succeed together in progressively harder challenges.

At last, Phase 3 represents the crew’s final preparation for leaving Earth and returning to their home planets. To complete this stage, players must collectively gather 25 units each of food, wood, and metal, alongside 50 unity points. In addition to resource collection, two new objectives are introduced. First, players must repair the engine of each spaceship, requiring five separate *Repair Engine* tasks to be completed. Second, they must construct five buckets, each designed to hold five units of food, wood, and metal, symbolising the distribution of provisions needed for their journey home (see right sidebar in Figure 20).

Figure 20. Videogame's main page during Phase 3

The task cards are updated accordingly, as seen in Figure 21, now featuring more advanced challenges and opportunities that provide greater rewards for food, wood, and metal. These higher-value tasks reflect the escalating difficulty of Phase 3 while giving players the means to meet the elevated thresholds.

 Uncommon Ground
Logout

PHASE 3: ESCAPE

Advanced Spear

Advanced Axe

Advanced Pickaxe

Advanced Hammer

MAKE BUCKET

BENEFITS:
+ 🪵 AND + 🍌🍌🍌

CONSEQUENCES:
- 🧟🧟🧟
- ❤️ for 🧟 OR
- ❤️❤️ for 🧟🧟🧟
Chosen alien is out for 1 turn

SKIPPING PENALTY:
- 🍌🍌

REQUIRED TOOL:
🪵

TURN OUT
SUGGEST SKIP

Food
🍌 20/25

Wood
🪵 31/25

Metal
🪨 20/25

Points
🍌 51/50

Spaceship
🚀 0/5

Bucket
🪵 0/5

john

❤️ 4/10

xi

❤️ 5/10

dev

❤️ 3/10

asia

❤️ 4/10

mpofu

❤️ 4/10

Figure 21. Task card page, during Phase 3

Once all conditions displayed on the right sidebar are fulfilled, the videogame presents a completion prompt confirming that the group has successfully finished the journey (see Figure 22). This message serves as both closure to the narrative and recognition of the collective effort, ensuring that all players are aware of their shared accomplishment.

Figure 22. Game completion prompt

Therefore, this last phase reinforces once more all five elements of the Positive Youth Development framework. Achieving the most demanding objectives builds **confidence**, as youth see their collective persistence pay off. Advanced tasks requiring strategy and foresight cultivate **competence**, highlighting planning and effective use of resources. Coordinating the repair of multiple ships and the distribution of supplies underscores **caring**, ensuring that no

one is left behind. The complexity of decisions at this stage, balancing limited resources against shared goals, strengthens **character** through fairness, responsibility, and resilience. Finally, as success depends entirely on teamwork and mutual reliance, **connection** is amplified, cementing the sense of unity built throughout the game.

3.4 TECHNICAL REQUIREMENTS AND ACCESS DETAILS

To maximise accessibility and inclusion, the game has been implemented as a browser-based application compatible with all major web platforms. Its responsive architecture ensures that the interface adapts seamlessly to a variety of devices, from desktop computers and laptops to tablets and smartphones, maintaining clarity, usability, and full functionality across formats. This design approach removes platform-specific barriers and broadens opportunities for participation, allowing youth to engage with the game regardless of their hardware.

The game is now hosted within Tampere University's infrastructure and can be accessed by individuals connected to the university network, either on-site or via virtual private network (VPN), through the link: <https://tie-gamehearts.rd.tuni.fi/>. Access is being temporarily restricted to the general population given the evaluation phase following this report (D5.5 Quantitative & qualitative analysis of the results).

Once the evaluation period ends, all data collection mechanisms will be removed, and the game will be made publicly available for broader dissemination.

All its code is already available at the link: <https://gitlab.tuni.fi/kdanto/gamehearts/> and the documentation in Appendix B.

4. NEXT STEPS

The immediate next step for game development is organising a series of co-design workshops with a larger scope. Participating stakeholders will consist of representatives from the target group (youth taking part in youth work services), youth workers, game designers, game developers, and other potential relevant stakeholders, for example, researchers in the areas of youth development. Here, the practical needs and challenges of youth and youth workers will play a significant role in influencing the narrative gameplay. By involving all these parties in a co-design process, we ensure that the game is inclusive to different players and targets relevant needs in appropriate ways. As a result of this second, more comprehensive workshop series, we will aim to have a fleshed-out gameplay and story that works in tandem real-life interactions.

5. REFERENCES

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APPENDIX A: List of all task cards

ID	Task name	Resource type	Reward, if completed	Skipping penalty	Alien specialist	Resource needed for completing task	Required tool	Phases available
1	Collect berries	Food	3 food units 3 unity points	-2 unity points	Glob	None	None	1 to 3
2	Collect mushrooms	Food	3 food units 3 unity points	-2 unity points	Glob	None	None	1 to 3
3	Collect fruits	Food	3 food units 3 unity points	-2 unity points	Glob	None	None	1 to 3
4	Collect twigs	Wood	2 wood units 3 unity points	-2 unity points	Splintertron	None	None	1 to 3
5	Collect reeds	Wood	2 wood units 3 unity points	-2 unity points	Splintertron	None	None	1 to 3
6	Collect logs	Wood	3 wood units 3 unity points	-2 unity points	Splintertron	None	None	1 to 3
7	Collect rocks	Metal	2 metal units 3 unity points	-2 unity points	Alloysius	None	None	1 to 3
8	Collect stones	Metal	2 metal units 3 unity points	-2 unity points	Alloysius	None	None	1 to 3
9	Collect flints	Metal	3 metal units 3 unity points	-2 unity points	Alloysius	None	None	1 to 3
10	Collect debris (5x) (one for each spaceship)	Spaceship	1 debris unit 3 unity points	-2 unity points	Dr. Fixle	None	None	Only 1st

ID	Task name	Resource type	Reward, if completed	Skipping penalty	Alien specialist	Resource needed for completing task	Required tool	Phases available
11	Make axe	Tools	1 axe 3 unity points	-2 unity points	Toolius	- 3 wood units - 2 metal units	None	Only 1st
12	Make pickaxe	Tools	1 pickaxe 3 unity points	-2 unity points	Toolius	- 3 wood units - 2 metal units	None	Only 1st
13	Make spear	Tools	1 spear 3 unity points	-2 unity points	Toolius	- 3 wood units - 2 metal units	None	Only 1st
14	Make hammer	Tools	1 hammer 3 unity points	-2 unity points	Toolius	- 3 wood units - 2 metal units	None	Only 1st
15	Hunt rabbit	Food	3 food units 3 unity points	-2 unity points	Glob	None	Spear	2 to 3
16	Hunt deer	Food	4 food units 3 unity points	-2 unity points	Glob	None	Spear	2 to 3
17	Cut pine tree	Wood	4 wood units 3 unity points	-2 unity points	Splintertron	None	Axe	2 to 3
18	Cut birch tree	Wood	4 wood units 3 unity points	-2 unity points	Splintertron	None	Axe	2 to 3
19	Cut conifer tree	Wood	4 wood units 3 unity points	-2 unity points	Splintertron	None	Axe	2 to 3
20	Mine iron	Metal	3 metal units 3 unity points	-2 unity points	Alloysius	None	Pickaxe	2 to 3
21	Mine aluminium	Metal	3 metal units 3 unity points	-2 unity points	Alloysius	None	Pickaxe	2 to 3
22	Mine silver	Metal	4 metal units 3 unity points	-2 unity points	Alloysius	None	Pickaxe	2 to 3

ID	Task name	Resource type	Reward, if completed	Skipping penalty	Alien specialist	Resource needed for completing task	Required tool	Phases available
23	Update axe	Tools	1 axe 3 unity points	-2 unity points	Toolius	- 2 wood units - 2 metal units	None	Only 2nd
24	Update pickaxe	Tools	1 pickaxe 3 unity points	-2 unity points	Toolius	- 2 wood units - 2 metal units	None	Only 2nd
25	Update spear	Tools	1 spear 3 unity points	-2 unity points	Toolius	- 2 wood units - 2 metal units	None	Only 2nd
26	Update hammer	Tools	1 hammer 3 unity points	-2 unity points	Toolius	- 2 wood units - 2 metal units	None	Only 2nd
27	Repair hull (5x) (one for each spaceship)	Spaceship	5 unity points	-2 unity points	Dr. Fixle	- 1 debris unit - 2 metal units	Hammer	Only 2nd
28	Repair engine (5x) (one for each spaceship)	Spaceship	1 engine repaired 3 unity points	-2 unity points	Dr. Fixle	None	Hammer	Only 3rd
29	Mine gold	Metal	5 metal units 3 unity points	-2 unity points	Alloysius	None	Pickaxe	Only 3rd
30	Cut willow tree	Wood	4 wood units 3 unity points	-2 unity points	Splintertron	None	Axe	Only 3rd
31	Cut oak tree	Wood	5 wood units 3 unity points	-2 unity points	Splintertron	None	Axe	Only 3rd
32	Hunt reindeer	Food	5 food units 3 unity points	-2 unity points	Glob	None	Spear	Only 3rd
33	Make bucket (5x) (one for each spaceship, to bring food to the trip back)	Tools	1 bucket 3 unity points	-2 unity points	Toolius	- 2 wood units	Hammer	Only 3rd

APPENDIX B: Technical documentation

Uncommon Ground is a web-based cooperative strategy game aiming to promote equity, diversity, and inclusion, built with PHP, MySQL, JavaScript, HTML, CSS, and WebSocket (Ratchet). Players register, log in, join groups, select unique aliens, and collaborate through turn-based voting mechanisms through phases involving resource management, tool upgrade and utilisation, and fulfilling phase-winning conditions.

Scope

The application includes a front-end interface built with HTML, CSS and JavaScript. It provides user-friendly, intuitive interaction during gameplay. The back-end is built with PHP. For live updates among players, Ratchet WebSocket has been incorporated.

System Information

The game is developed on Microsoft Windows 11 Enterprise machine. XAMPP software suite and VSCode IDE have been used for setting development environments.

Installation and commands

- For installing composer: `apt install composer`.
- For installing Ratchet: `composer require cboden/ratchet`
- To run WebSocket server: `php websocket/server.php`

Architecture & Directory Layout

Path	Purpose
index.php, login/, register/	Authentication and onboarding.
group/	Group selection and membership logic.
alien/	Character selection, readiness, and game start management.
game/	Core gameplay: phases, cards, resources, tools, and voting.
includes/	Shared JS utilities: header controls, password toggles, clientside logging.
websocket/	Ratchet-based realtime server (<i>server.php</i>) and client wrapper (<i>socket.js</i>).
images/, styles.css	Static assets and styling.
db.php, database.sql	Database connection and schema.
vendor/	Composer dependencies (Ratchet).

Authentication Flow

Registration (*register/registration.php, register/register.php*)

- Validates username, password client-side (*register.js*).
- Stores new users in users table with hashed passwords.

Login (*index.php, login/login.php*)

- Session-based authentication; credentials verified against users.
- Successful login sets `$_SESSION['username']` and redirects to group selection.

Session Enforcement (*includes/session_redirect.php*)

- Redirected users to the appropriate page based on session state (login, group selection, alien selection, or game phase).

Group Management

Group Selection (*group/group_selection.php, group/group.php*)

- Players enter a group code to join.
- Server associates users with groups via *group_users* and records membership in session.
- Concurrent entries are prevented.

Alien Selection & Game Start

UI (*alien/alien_selection.php, alien/main.js, alien/alien.js*)

- Displays carousel of aliens from the *aliens* table.
- Players choose a character; selections stored in *selected_aliens*.
- Realtime updates through websockets ensure other players see selections immediately.

alien/main.js (alien selection page coordinator)

Handles page initialization, WebSocket updates, and readiness tracking for starting the game.

Initialization

- Imports: `setupWebSocket`, `loadAliens`, `checkReady`, `setupHeaderControls`, and `logAction`.
- `window.onload`:
 - Calls `setupHeaderControls()` to wire up navigation buttons (logout/back).
 - Initializes a single websocket via `setupWebSocket(callback)`:
 - `update_group_` or `alien-update`: Reload the alien grid (`loadAliens`) and re-evaluate startbutton conditions (`checkReady`).

- *start_ready_update*: Refetch readiness data only.
- *game_start*: Double checks with *check_start_ready.php* and, if the group has already started, redirects to the game phase (*../game/phase*).
- Immediately loads aliens and readiness state on page load.

Start Button Logic

- Event binding (DOMContentLoaded): If *#start-btn* exists, clicking it:
 1. Logs the action.
 2. Toggles the player's ready state and sends it to *mark_start_ready.php*.
 3. Updates button dataset/text to reflect current readiness counts.
 4. Broadcasts "game_start" if everyone is ready (server signals start), otherwise "start_ready_update" to keep other clients in sync.

alien/alien.js (alien grid rendering & startreadiness logic)

Contains functions used by main.js for rendering the alien carousel and controlling the "Start" button.

State & Globals

- **currentUser**: username of the loggedin player (filled by *loadAliens*).
- **userHasSelected**: whether this user currently owns an alien.
- **resizeListener**: reference to the resize callback used by the carousel controls.

loadAliens()

Fetches *get_alien.php* and renders a card for each alien in *#alien-grid*.

- Builds card HTML with name, image, ability, description, who selected it, and a "Select/Unselect" button.
- The button is disabled if the user already selected a different alien.
- Tracks selection state (*currentUser*, *userHasSelected*).
- Calls *setupCarouselControls()* after rendering.

window.selectAlien(id)

Global function triggered by each card's button.

- Sends { *alien_id*: id } to *select_alien.php*.
- On success, updates *userHasSelected*, sends WebSocket "alien-update" (via imported socket), and logs the action (selected or unselected).

checkReady()

Determines if the "Start" button should be enabled.

- Calls *check_start_ready.php*.

- If the game already started (started flag), redirects to “../game/phase”.
- Otherwise toggles #start-btn disabled state, color, dataset, and label (START vs UNREADY + counts) depending on group readiness and whether the user is marked ready.

setupCarouselControls()

Provides horizontal scrolling for the alien grid.

- Identifies left/right arrows (#scroll-left/#scroll-right) and the grid.
- `updateArrowVisibility()` hides arrows if all cards fit within the container.
- `scrollRight()/scrollLeft()` rotate cards by reordering DOM elements (infinite carousel style).
- Registers `updateArrowVisibility` on window resize (stores listener in `resizeListener` to avoid duplicates).

Readiness & Start (`check_start_ready.php`, `mark_start_ready.php`)

- Each player marks themselves ready and readiness is tracked in `group_readiness`.
- When each alien is uniquely represented and all players are ready, the game phase begins (`game/phase.php`).

Gameplay Phases

Phase Layout (`game/phase.php`)

- Displays current phase, tools, cards, resources, player status, and action buttons (store, health recovery).

Main Client Logic (`game/main.js`, `game/game.js`)

- Handles ready/unready toggles, card loading, tool/resource display, voting modals, and phase transitions.
- Reacts to WebSocket messages to update UI, initiate votes, or reload state.

`game/main.js` (websocket-orchestrated game flow)

This script initializes the game page, listens to WebSocket messages, and coordinates UI updates by calling functions from `game.js`.

Initialization

- Imports: Various UI and state-management functions from `game.js`, `setupWebSocket` for realtime communication.
- Startup:
 - On `DOMContentLoaded`, initializes phase UI, loads player data, tools, resources, and binds buttons (`setupReadyButton`, `setupStoreButton`, `setupRecoveryButton`, `setupBackToGameButton`, `loadCurrentCard`).
 - On `window.load`, ensures a websocket “`update_phase`” notification is sent when the client joins.

- On *beforeunload*, notifies others that the phase might have changed.

WebSocket Handler

setupWebSocket(callback) opens a single connection and invokes the callback on every message.

Handled message types:

Type	Effect
start_vote	Opens vote modal via <i>showVoteModal</i> .
vote_result	Displays outcome (<i>showVoteOutcomeModal</i>), refreshes resources/tools/player status, reloads current card, optionally triggers <i>pollPhaseCompletion</i> .
start_recovery_vote	Opens health recovery vote (<i>showRecoveryVoteModal</i>).
recovery_vote_result	Shows result, refreshes resources/players, clears selections, reloads recovery options.
start_store_vote	Opens resource purchase vote (<i>showStoreVoteModal</i>).
store_vote_result	Shows result, refreshes resources, clears store selections, reloads store options, may call <i>pollPhaseCompletion</i> .
store_update heal_update	Synchronizes numeric inputs (store/recovery) across clients via DOM updates and localStorage.
resource_blocked	Disables volunteer button and checks for game over.
game_over	Triggers <i>showGameOverModal</i> .

Raw string messages:

- “**update_readybtn**”: Forces card reloads and locks ready button.
- “**update_phase**”: Reloads player status, buttons, resources.
- “**update_tools**”: Refreshes tools display.
- “**update_readycount**”: Polls readiness counts to update button label.
- “**phase_confirm_update**”: Updates “proceed to next phase” button counts.
- “**phase_advanced**”: Reloads page when phase is advanced.

game/game.js (UI & game logic helpers)

Contains all DOM-manipulation and fetch logic used by the game page. Key exports:

Player & Card State

- **loadPlayerStatus()**: Fetches player data, sorts by alien, displays health/alien

icons, binds info popups, updates volunteer availability.

- **loadCurrentCard():** Determines whether to show a task card, fetches card details, renders benefits/consequences/required tools, handles resource shortages, binds volunteer/skip buttons, and hides ready/action controls when a card is active.

Volunteer/Readiness Management

- **updateVolunteerButtonState():** Enables or disables the volunteer button based on resources, health, or player availability; also marks players who can't participate.
- **checkGameOverState():** Notifies server and shows game-over modal if both volunteer and skip actions are blocked.
- **setupReadyButton():** Restores ready/unready state from server, updates label counts, toggles other action buttons, handles ready/unready toggling, and broadcasts updates.

Store & Recovery Navigation

- **setupStoreButton()/setupRecoveryButton():** Switches to store or recovery view; loads corresponding options.
- **clearStoreSelections()/clearRecoverySelections():** Resets quantity inputs and related localStorage.
- **setupBackToGameButton():** Returns from store/recovery to main game view and clears selections.

Resource & Tool Display

- **loadResources():** Fetches resource levels and caps, renders colored progress bars, updates phase data.
- **loadTools():** Lists primitive/advanced tools, shows cooldown/unavailable states with appropriate icons.

Voting System

- **showVoteModal(action, initiator, alienImage, cardId):** Opens vote modal for card actions.
- **showWaitingModal():** Displays “waiting for others” message.
- **showVoteOutcomeModal(message):** Shows pass/fail result temporarily.
- **showGameOverModal():** Shows “game over” dialog with *logout* button.
- **checkVoteResultLoop() / sendVote(vote):** Submits yes/no vote for current card action and polls until consensus is reached.

Recovery Votes

- **showRecoveryVoteModal(target, alienImage, amount, initiator, initiatorAlien):** Vote modal for healing a player.
- **sendRecoveryVote(vote)/checkRecoveryVoteResultLoop():** Submit and tally

recovery votes.

Store Votes

- **loadStoreOptions():** Builds store UI, capped by available points; syncs input changes via WebSocket.
- **showStoreVoteModal(resource, amount, initiator, initiatorAlien):** Vote modal for purchasing resources.
- **sendStoreVote(vote)/checkStoreVoteResultLoop():** Submit and tally store votes.

Recovery Options

- **loadRecoveryOptions():** Builds healing UI based on current food and player health and synchronizes input changes via websocket.

Phase Progression

- **updatePhaseUI():** Enables the “next phase” button based on server-flag *canAdvancePhase*.
- **pollPhaseCompletion():** Polls server for phase completion; if met, shows confirmation modal managed by internal *showPhaseCompleteModal()* (handles unanimous proceed votes and phase advancement).

Supporting Utilities (internal)

- Rendering helpers (*renderIcons, repeatIcons, renderAlienIcons, getIconForKey*), health-cost calculations, player marking, and alien info pop-up management.

Card Mechanics

- Drawing Cards: *draw_card.php* selects a card based on phase and inventory constraints, decrements tool cooldowns, and updates turn count.
- Current Card State: *get_current_card.php* return card details, required tools, and player availability.

Voting System

- Start Vote: *start_vote.php* initiates volunteer or skip votes for a card action; also validates resource availability.
- Submit Vote: *submit_vote.php* records individual yes/no votes.
- Tally Votes: *tally_votes.php* checks unanimity; if passed, applies card benefits/penalties, tool cooldowns, resource deductions, and health changes.
- Similar mechanisms exist for recovery votes (*start_recovery_vote.php, submit_recovery_vote.php, tally_recovery_vote.php*) and store votes (*start_store_vote.php, submit_store_vote.php, tally_store_vote.php*).

Readiness & Turn Flow

- Players mark readiness via *mark_ready.php*. Once all ready, card drawing occurs and readiness resets (*check_ready_status.php*).
- *get_phase_status.php* reports whether a card is shown. *update_readybtn*

websocket messages synchronize buttons across clients.

Resources & Tools

- Resource Management: *get_resources.php*, *update_resources.php* manage group resources with phase-dependent caps stored in *phase_caps*.
- Tool Management: *get_tools.php* returns tool levels and cooldowns from *group_tools*.

Player State

- *get_player_data.php* provides health, availability, and alien icons for all players; *update_health.php* adjusts individual health.

WebSocket Messaging

- Client (*socket.js*): Creates a single WebSocket connection to “ws://localhost:8080” and dispatches incoming messages.
- Server (*server.php*): Broadcasts plain-text signals (e.g., *alien-update*, *update_phase*) and structured JSON events for voting and resource updates.

Logging

- Client actions are logged via *includes/logger.js* calling *log_event.php*, which stores events in logs for auditing.

Database Schema Highlights

- Core Tables: *users*, *groups*, *group_users*, *aliens*, *selected_aliens*.
- Gameplay: *group_readiness*, *group_status*, *group_resources*, *group_tools*, *group_votes*, *card_votes*, *cards*, *card_phases*.
- Voting Extensions: *recovery_votes* & *recovery_vote_responses*, *store_votes* & *store_vote_responses*, *phase_confirmations*.
- Each table supports specific gameplay mechanics (*readiness tracking*, *resource*

caps, tool states, voting outcomes).

Figure 22. UML class diagram for database schema

Utility Modules

- *includes/header.js*

Adds “Back” (leave group) and “Logout” buttons with confirmation dialogs, cleaning up database entries and sessions as needed.

- *includes/eye.js*

Toggles password visibility in login/register forms.

- *styles.css*

Central stylesheet for consistent layout and responsive design.

Credit Page

- Contains project information, disclaimer, licence, and third-party resources' attributions.

DISCLAIMER

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CONTACT

Website: <https://gamehearts.eu/>

Email: info@gamehearts.eu

GAMEHEARTS Partners

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